

Study to search for transition state and ternary complex formation of Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin B₁ system : A polarographic approach

Firoj Khan and Farid Khan*

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S Gour University, Sagar-470 003, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 1 April 2004, accepted 3 March 2006

Abstract : Polarographic technique was used to study the exact position of transition state between dropping mercury electrode and mercury solution interface and also to study the ternary complex formation of Mn^{II} using neomycin, chlor-tetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and vitamin B₁ (thiamine) as secondary ligand at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄ at 298 K. The Mn^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 complexes. The nature of electrode process was quasi-reversible and the "transition state" was formed in exact mid of dropping mercury electrode and solution interface which was confirmed on the basis of kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ), diffusion coefficient (D) and standard rate constant (k).

Keywords : Ternary complex, polarography, manganese(II) complex.

Manganese is an essential element present in all living organisms. The primary uses of manganese in medicines are as germicides and antiseptic. Manganese is required for the activity of some dehydrogenases, decarboxylases, kinases, oxidases and peroxidases¹. On the otherhand, antibiotics are natural compounds produced mostly by plant microorganisms used against fungal and bacterial diseases in plants and living things². Vitamin B₁ is an important vitamin B complex given simultaneously with other drugs for serious diseases³, therefore, the study of [Mn^{II}-antibiotics-vitamin B₁] system has great importance. The values of stability constants of these complexes gave an idea to use these antibiotics and vitamin B₁ against Mn toxicity and the values of α confirmed the position of "transition state" in these electrokinetic reactions.

Results and discussion

Mn^{II} gave two-electron quasi-reversible reduction wave in 1.0 M NaClO₄ using 0.001% Triton X-100 (suppressor) at pH 7.30-8.40⁴ at 298 K, but pH 7.30 ± 0.01 was selected for the present study to study the complex formation in human blood pH. Pure hydrogen gas was passed through the test solution before recording the current voltage data. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was added in the test solution to stabilise the pH of the analyte.

[Mn-vitamin B₁] system :

The concentration of metal, NaClO₄ and Triton X-100 in the test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. The concentration of vitamin B₁ varied from 10 mM to 50 mM. The shift of E_{1/2} became more negative on increasing the concentration of vitamin B₁, showing complex formation. The current voltage curves were quasi-reversible. The E_{1/2}^{reversible} from E_{1/2}^{quasi-reversible} values were determined by Gellings method⁵. Lingane's treatment⁶ of the data confirmed the formation of 1 : 1, and 1 : 2 complexes with stability constant log β₀₁ = 2.00 and log β₀₂ = 3.15 respectively. The values of stability constants were given in Table 1.

[Mn-antibiotics-vitamin B₁] system :

In this system, the E_{1/2} also became more negative with the addition of [vitamin B₁] to the binary system [Mn-antibiotics] showed ternary complex formation. The concentration of Mn^{II}, NaClO₄ and Triton X-100 were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. The concentration of antibiotics varies from 1.0 mM to 30 mM at constant concentration of vitamin B₁ i.e. 0.025 M and 0.05 M respectively. E_{1/2}^r from E_{1/2}^q values were determined by Gellings method⁵. Kinetic parameters were determined by Tamamushi and Tanaka method⁷. Schaap and McMaster method⁸ was used to confirm the formation of 1 : 1 : 1,

Table 1. Stability constant values of [Mn-antibiotics-vitamin B₁] system^a

Mn^{II} = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. 298 K

Ligands	log β ₀₁	log β ₀₂	log β ₁₀ ⁴	log β ₂₀ ⁴	log β ₃₀ ⁴	log β ₁₁	log β ₁₂	log β ₂₁
Neomycin	-	-	2.65	4.85	7.00	3.41	5.23	7.70
Chlortetracycline	-	-	3.31	5.02	7.78	4.19	5.45	8.12
Oxytetracycline	-	-	4.00	-	8.13	-	7.13	8.40
Tetracycline	-	-	4.12	7.13	-	4.50	7.62	8.67
Penicillin-V	-	-	4.31	7.76	8.60	4.68	-	8.98
Penicillin-G	-	-	4.40	8.00	9.00	4.80	8.51	9.47
Vitamin B ₁	2.00	3.15	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aStability constants for other systems can be sent on request.

Table 2. Polarographic data and F_{ij}[X, Y] function of [Mn-neomycin-vitamin B₁] system^a

Mn^{II} = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. 298 K

[Neo.] × 10 ³	log (I _m /I _c)	E _{1/2} ^r - V vs SCE	F ₀₀ [X, Y]	F ₁₀ [X, Y] × 10 ³	F ₂₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁵	F ₃₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁶	log (I _m /I _c)	E _{1/2} ^r - V vs SCE	F ₀₀ [X, Y]	F ₁₀ [X, Y] × 10 ³	F ₂₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁵	F ₃₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁶
		[Vitamin] = 0.025 M						[Vitamin] = 0.05 M				
0.00	-	1.400	-	-	-	-	-	1.400	-	-	-	-
1.00	0.0075	1.436	16.83	12.45	13.33	10.00	0.0152	1.451	55.14	45.61	25.86	10.01
2.00	0.0152	1.444	32.00	13.81	13.43	10.01	0.0230	1.459	105.96	48.21	25.96	10.00
3.00	0.0230	1.449	49.93	15.18	13.53	10.00	0.0310	1.464	162.06	50.84	26.06	10.00
4.00	0.0230	1.454	70.69	16.57	13.63	10.00	0.0310	1.468	223.49	53.49	26.16	10.02
5.00	0.0310	1.457	94.33	17.99	13.73	10.00	0.0310	1.471	290.32	56.15	26.26	10.00
6.00	0.0310	1.460	120.93	19.42	13.83	10.02	0.0391	1.474	362.59	58.84	26.36	10.00
8.00	0.0391	1.465	183.20	22.35	14.03	10.02	0.0474	1.478	523.75	64.27	26.56	10.03
10.00	0.0474	1.469	257.98	25.36	14.23	10.01	0.0558	1.482	707.58	69.80	26.78	10.02
20.00	0.0558	1.484	836.32	41.59	15.23	10.00	0.0558	1.490	1980.67	98.55	27.76	10.00
30.00	0.0558	1.494	1801.29	59.89	16.25	10.01	0.0644	1.510	3889.22	129.32	28.76	10.01
log A = 0.64, log B = 4.04, log C = 6.12, log D = 7.00						log A = 0.97, log B = 4.63, log C = 6.41, log D = 7.00						

^aF_{ij}[X, Y] functions for other systems are available on request.

1 : 2 : 1 and 1 : 1 : 2 complexes. The values of function F_{ij}(X, Y) against X, where X = primary ligand i.e. neomycin and Y = secondary ligand i.e. vitamin B₁, i and j are their stoichiometric numbers were given in Table 2.

The plots of $\left(E - \frac{0.0591}{n} \log \frac{i_d - i}{i}\right)$ against *i* are linear

and the plots of F_{ij}[X, Y] vs *i* are also linear (Fig. 1). The values of kinetic parameters were given in Table 3. The plots between (E_{1/2}^r - E) against log (Z - 1) are all linear. The values of Z is given by the following equation⁹.

$$Z = \text{anti log} \left\{ \frac{nF}{2.303} (E_{1/2}^r - E) \right\} + \log \frac{i_d - i}{i}$$

To compare the stability of binary and ternary complexes, the values of mixing constant log K_m¹⁰ was calculated for each system. The values are 0.59, 0.105, -0.64, -0.775 and 0.775 for [Mn-neo.-vit. B₁], [Mn-chlortetra.-vit. B₁], [Mn-tetracy.-vit. B₁], [Mn-pen.V-vit. B₁] and [Mn-pen.G-vit. B₁] systems respectively. The positive values showed that the ternary complex is more stable than its binary complex while negative value⁵ showed that binary complex is more stable than its ternary complex. Since 1 : 1 : 1 complex is not formed for [Mn-oxytetra.-vit. B₁] system, therefore the value of log K_m was not calculated.

It is clear from the values of stability constant (Table 1), that the trend of stability constant of ternary complexes was neomycin < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < penicillin-V < penicillin-G. The

Fig. 1. [Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin B₁] system.

complex [Mn-neo.-vit. B₁] has the lowest stability among all the selected antibiotics might be due to the considerable steric hindrance between various groups present in neomycin¹¹ and Mn^{II}. In case of tetracyclines, all the selected tetracyclines have the same structures except in the difference in R₁ and R₂. The lesser stability of chlortetracycline than that of oxytetracycline can be explained on the basis of electronegative Cl present at R₁ in the former than in the later, where H is present at R₁ therefore, Cl attracts electrons more rapidly than H causing more electronic disturbances in chlortetracycline than that of oxytetracycline¹². In case of tetracycline H is present both at R₁ and R₂, therefore, it, has least electronic disturbance in comparison to other tetracyclines, causes the greatest stability of its complexes amongst other tetracycline complexes. This order of stability is also in accordance with the pK values¹³ of these tetracyclines. In case of penicillin-V and penicillin-G, the ring nitrogen and oxygen of carboxylic acid may take part in bond formation with Mn. The greater stability of penicillin-G complexes than that of penicillin-V complexes is due to the electronegative oxygen present in penicillin-V, as a result of which, the steric hindrance is more in penicillin-V than in penicillin-G causing the greater stability of penicillin-V complex than that of penicillin-V complexes.

The values of stability constants of ternary complexes varied from 3.41 to 9.47, while in case of binary complexes, the stability varied from 2.00 to 9.00, therefore, on the basis of these data, it can be concluded that, any of the selected antibiotics or vitamin B₁ alone or with joint

Table 3. Kinetic parameters of [Mn-neomycin-vitamin B₁] system^a

Mn ^{II} = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO ₄ , pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. 298 K												
[Neo.] × 10 ³	E _{1/2} ^q - V vs SCE	Slope (mV)	α	λ s ^{-1/2}	D ^{1/2} × 10 ³ cm ² s ⁻¹	K × 10 ³ cm s ⁻¹	E _{1/2} ^q - V vs SCE	Slope (mV)	α	λ s ^{-1/2}	D ^{1/2} × 10 ³ cm ² s ⁻¹	K × 10 ³ cm s ⁻¹
[Vitamin B ₁] = 0.025 M						[Vitamin B ₁] = 0.05 M						
0.00	1.410	40	0.43	2.54	3.82	9.70	1.410	40	0.43	2.54	3.82	9.70
1.00	1.455	35	0.43	1.22	3.76	4.60	1.470	35	0.42	0.90	3.69	3.33
2.00	1.460	40	0.52	1.60	3.69	5.93	1.480	35	0.52	1.07	3.62	3.89
3.00	1.470	36	0.50	1.60	3.62	5.82	1.485	38	0.48	1.07	3.55	3.82
4.00	1.480	38	0.48	1.73	3.62	4.12	1.485	35	0.47	0.760	3.55	2.70
5.00	1.495	38	0.45	1.80	3.55	6.41	1.490	38	0.45	1.27	3.55	4.54
6.00	1.500	35	0.52	1.13	3.55	4.04	1.505	38	0.47	1.60	3.49	5.61
8.00	1.510	35	0.48	1.13	3.49	3.97	1.515	35	0.42	1.80	3.42	6.17
10.00	1.515	38	0.42	1.51	3.42	5.19	1.520	35	0.50	1.07	3.36	3.60
20.00	1.520	38	0.50	1.01	3.84	3.40	1.530	38	0.46	1.43	3.36	4.81
30.00	1.525	35	0.48	2.40	3.36	8.08	1.540	35	0.43	1.91	3.29	6.29

^aKinetic parameters for other systems can be sent on request.

can be successful to reduce the toxicity of Mn in living things.

The values of kinetic parameters (Table 3) have great importance in kinetics. The values of standard rate constant varied from 2.70×10^{-3} to $9.70 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ confirmed that the electrode processes were quasi-reversible. The values of transfer coefficient varied from 0.42 to 0.52 confirmed that "transition state" formed in exact mid of the dropping mercury electrode and solution interface¹⁴. The values of activation Gibbs function (ΔG^\ddagger) in the present case is $\Delta G^\ddagger + 1/2F\Delta\phi$ ¹⁵, where F is Faraday of electricity and $\Delta\phi$ is the difference of potential between d.m.e. and solution interface. The values of degree of irreversibility (λ) varied from 0.76 to 2.54 $\text{s}^{-1/2}$ are also as expected from the results (Table 3).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. A manual polarograph using Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer was used to record the current voltage data. Latinin and Lingane cell and dropping mercury electrode were used. The polarographic capillary was 5 cm long having diameter 0.04 mm with $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.02 cm (calculated) effective height of mercury¹⁶. The pH of the solution was recorded on Elico digital pH meter fitted with glass and saturated calomel electrode. The pH was adjusted to 7.30 ± 0.01 with dilute solutions of NaOH and HClO₄ as required. The resistance of the cell was lesser than 200 Ω therefore no correction was made for IR.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar for providing the laboratory facilities.

References

1. J. Harte, C. Holden, R. Schnieder and C. Shirtley, "Toxic A to Z", University of California Press, Oxford, 1991.
2. A. K. Kesharwani and F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2002, **18**, 413.
3. R. W. Vitter, *Am. J. Clin. Nutrition*, 1976, **4**, 378.
4. F. Khan and L. Tantuvoy, *J. Pharm. and Biomed. Anal. (Netherland)*, 2002, **27**, 933.
5. P. J. Gellings, *Z. Electrochem. Bunsenges Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 477, 481; 1963, **67**, 167.
6. J. J. Lingane, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **29**, 1.
7. R. Tamamushi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Newfolge*, 1963, **39**, 117.
8. W. B. Schaap and D. L. McMaster, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4999.
9. R. Tamamushi, K. Ishibashi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Physik Chem., New Folge*, 1962, **35**, 211.
10. S. Vajhallya and F. Khan, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1999, **72**, 397.
11. F. Khan and L. Tantuvoy, *Trans. SAEST*, 2000, **35**, 79.
12. P. Matthews, "Advanced Chemistry", ed. Low Price, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1996.
13. J. M. Desiqueria, S. Carvalho, E. B. Paniago, L. Tosi and H. Beraldo, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1994, **83**, 291.
14. F. Khan and L. Tantuvoy, *Oxid. Commun. (Bulgaria)*, 2000, **23**, 629.
15. P. W. Atkins, "Physical Chemistry", W. H. Freeman and Co., San Francisco, 1978.
16. L. Meites, "Polarographic Technique", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1965, 2nd ed., 131.